

Marketing Abilities and Innovative Abilities that Affect the Performance of Entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province

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Abstract:- This research aims to study the marketing ability of entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province, which consists of Product development, price, distribution channels and marketing communications and innovation capabilities that include process innovation and management innovations that affect the performance of entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province are qualitative research. The sample group used in this study There are 30 entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan province using content analysis techniques, a technique for analyzing data from reality.

The results of the study found that marketing ability and innovation capabilities of entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province is at a high level, especially in terms of products and distribution channels in terms of innovation ability It was found that at a high level, both process innovation and management innovation, entrepreneurs used more technology. Employees in the organization are encouraged to learn more leading to successful operations in the organization.

Keywords:- Marketing Capability; Innovation Capability; Organizational Performance; Entrepreneurship.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the years Companies or organizations Become more aware of the importance of product development Products are created to be novel. modern including customers receive business information quickly through multiple channels. Advertising and public relations, usinesses need to have strategies in place to help drive product purchases. Find ways to maintain good relationships with customers and explore the market more to bring in customer information to create satisfaction, Competitors come together to modify or analyze data. Customer behavior in finding new target customer groups and market leadership leading to new marketing excellence and improved efficiency. Indicates a new competitive strategy is ability Performance in planning marketing formats that creates a strategy of difference customer focus that is a specific target group which results in

achieving the goals set by the organization Moreover, the organization that have strong market potential and the ability to create innovations can create a competitive advantage for businesses in the long run (Alan, 2016)

Innovation capability is an important factor and pillar that makes a business successful and globally recognized. Any business that cannot invest in research and development to create new innovations cannot survive (Okrah & Agbozo, 2018, pp. 230). Innovation capabilities will become an essential part of businesses of all sizes. Especially in business (Khorshid, 2019, pp. 1). (Teece Pisano & Shuen, 1997) Entrepreneurs who can adjust their business model to be in line with continuous change will can increase competitiveness in marketing (Jean & Kim, 2020) but Jeong Jin and Jung (2019). Entrepreneurs have lower marketing skills and abilities than large organizations, such as marketing communications. Product development and online distribution channel management, which after the application of the Internet (Internet) to businesses, has opened up opportunities and increased communication channels between entrepreneurs and customers, increasing opportunities for SMEs to build relationships. with customers anywhere Can find new markets more easily. Moon and Jain (2007) found that an organization's marketing capabilities are a key success factor and a link that helps increase entrepreneurs' web capabilities. to be so high that marketing efficiency can be increased (Jean & Kim, 2020)

Organizations and industrial factories in Samut Prakan Province are important to strengthen the country's economy and can spread prosperity. Jobs are created Create added value Create income for the country (Office of Small and Medium Enterprises Promotion, 2019). From the said issue It can be seen that marketing ability it can be seen that marketing ability and innovation ability are important factors that will affect the competitive advantage and performance of an organization. And Samut Prakan Province is one of the economically important provinces in Thailand. Because there are many industrial factories This made the researcher interested in studying the influence of marketing ability and

innovation ability on the operations of entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province.

A. Objectives of the study

- To study marketing abilities that influence the performance of entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province.
- To study innovation capabilities that influence the performance of entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province.

B. Expected benefits

- Entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province can use the information obtained from the study to plan business management. This will result in a competitive advantage and further organizational performance.
- Relevant agencies can use the information obtained from the study as a guideline for business development of entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province.

C. Research Conceptual Framework

From the study and review of literature Related research It can be summarized as a conceptual framework as follows:

Fig 1: Research conceptual framework

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Market Capability

Definition of marketing competence

Marketing ability means managing operations regarding marketing channels and reaching customer groups. Marketing communications that make customers aware of news and analysis needs and maintaining good relationships with customers as well as creating a network of business partners Marketing management is considered a management resource used to increase competitiveness. and financial performance of the business with a marketing strategy driven by seeking activities Increased marketing benefits Darroch & McNaughton (2002) such as finding new distribution channels and finding ways to reach more customer groups.

Bagozzi, 1998 states that marketing capability refers to the ability to take advantage of available knowledge, technology, and resources to create customer satisfaction. The success of entrepreneurs comes from creating value for customers. Develop products and services Including developing better marketing abilities. Entrepreneurs need to have good market information. Marketing technology has been developed. Improve your marketing skills and management abilities to increase your competitiveness. and (Bagozzi, 1998) further suggested that entrepreneurial competence depends on the close relationship between the

entrepreneur and the customer. Such good relationships will lead to the development of new products and new services.

Kotler (1994) stated that factors affecting the marketing ability of small and medium-sized enterprises include many factors such as Customer satisfaction Kotler (1994) refers to as a concept related to factors that affect customer satisfaction. which consists of Product quality, Quality of service Atmosphere of the place, product price, product value Product features Also includes delivery time. and after-sales service.

Promotion is a marketing activity that can stimulate sales immediately, such as various promotions, temporary price reductions to increase sales. Sales promotions have three goals: (1) sales promotions directed at consumers; In order to induce a greater number of purchases. Make a quick purchasing decision or have a desire to try out the product (2) Promotion Sales directed to middlemen It is a sales promotion aimed at middlemen. distributors or sellers to encourage intermediaries to introduce new products or products Encourage intermediaries to buy and keep products for sale in larger quantities. (3) Promotions directed at employees or sales departments to be able to sell more products. It is an encouragement to find new customers or find organizers Additional sales to the company Sales promotion is an activity that is often combined with advertising or selling using salespeople, such as advertising to know that there are discounts, exchanges, giveaways, or sending salespeople to hand out product samples from door to door. In the context of small and medium enterprises, sales promotion is the entrepreneur has a method or various activities that stimulate customers to be more interested in purchasing products through various methods such as price reductions, exchange discounts, giveaways, or installments (Bartels and Robert, 1998). Have the ability to analyze the market analysis allows entrepreneurs to identify and define market opportunities. Able to identify problems Find a way to solve the problem Evaluate operations Check marketing performance Understand the marketing environment Understand customer needs, such as what types of products meet customer needs at what time do customers buy products, including being able to analyze the company's income Inventory care These elements are an indication of an entrepreneur's marketing ability (Hollander et al, 2005).

Distribution channels refer to the channels through which products move from producers to consumers. There are 2 types of distribution channels: (1) Direct distribution channel means selling products from the manufacturer to consumers, without middlemen. (2) Indirect distribution channel means the channel through which products move from the manufacturer. By having to go through a middleman to the consumer. Each channel has advantages. The disadvantages vary depending on the nature and abilities of the operator. Having a variety of distribution channels will allow entrepreneurs to sell more products. Moreover, nowadays selling products online is widely popular. It is fast and convenient (Weitz and Wansley, 2002). The location of the store is appropriate. The principle for choosing a location for a retail store is that it must be a prominent location. There

is a place for parking. And it is already a place where people are crowded. Retail stores also need to choose locations according to their target groups for example, The stationery store should be near the school. Fashion clothing stores should also be in shopping centers. A la carte restaurants should be located in dormitories. A coffee shop is in a meeting place, etc. Another strategy for choosing a location for a retail store is the store should be located in an area that has attractions. For example, Department stores, movie theaters, fast food restaurants, etc., were These will be a good way to attract customers. Having stores located nearby, customers who come to use those locations may also come to use our services in our stores (Tedlow and Geoffrey, 2014). Try to maintain as many customer bases as possible. A customer base is a group of customers who purchase products or services regularly. These customers are the main source of income for the operators. Entrepreneurs need to understand customer behavior through market research or observation of past behavior. Maintaining the customer base can be an important

factor that allows entrepreneurs to grow steadily. (Christensen, Clayton and Raynor, 2003). Speed of bringing products to market It is a method for delivering products or services to the market as quickly as possible in order to respond to customer needs in a timely manner. Being able to bring products to the market before other entrepreneurs can bring good results in many ways. For example: (1) increasing the competitiveness of entrepreneurs Because presenting products to the target group quickly allows products to reach customers before other entrepreneurs. Affects decision making in selecting products. (2) Bringing products to market first allows entrepreneurs to dominate those markets before other entrepreneurs. Even if those products are not of poor quality. (3) Bringing products to market first makes our products more well-known than products that come later (Weitz and Wansley, 2002).

The table shows content information from the marketing capability literature review (Marketing Capability)

Table 1: Marketing capabilities

Researcher	Content	Attribute
Hollander et al, 2005	Market analysis	Have the ability to analyze the market, such as market characteristics and ability to enter the market
Bartels and Robert, 1998	There are channels to sell products.	There are various channels for selling products, both in store and online.
Kotler (1994)	relationship	Have a good relationship with customers, such as having customer service after the sale. or providing useful information to customers
Tedlow and Geoffrey, 2014	Location	The location of the establishment is appropriate and easily visible, making it convenient for customers to purchase products.
Christensen, Clayton and Raynor, 2003	customer	Always trying to expand the customer group, such as finding new markets or new customer groups

Source: Economic and Business article www.patani-economy.com

From the above literature review Marketing ability is the ability of entrepreneurs to use their knowledge, technology, and resources to create customer satisfaction. Including being able to increase sales as targeted. The components of marketing capability include: (1) Have the ability to analyze the market, such as market characteristics and the ability to enter the market (2) have regular promotions or discounts for customers (3) Have a variety of channels for selling products in the store. (4) Have good relationships with customers, such as having after-sales customer service. or providing useful information to customers. (5) Always trying to expand customer groups, such as finding new markets or new customer groups. (6) The location of the establishment is appropriate and easily visible, allowing customers to buy products convenient. 4. Strategic innovation (STI) is an innovation using strategies to add value to products and services so that consumers can recognize and experience them. and gain direct experience from using the product This includes using new marketing methods. Strategic innovation can create satisfaction for consumers. The organization's strategy and operational plans must be coordinated and Support innovation The organization has a system or process for systematically testing errors, failures, and risks in any decision making through various techniques such as scenario Management and the ability to coordinate the behavior of community enterprises to be consistent with the condition The

competitive environment of the organization (Wang & Ahmed, 2004)

B. Innovation Capabilities

Innovation Capabilities arise from creativity by combining strategic approaches. with the organization's innovative behavior and processes in producing new products to the market (Wang & Ahmed, 2004), including the organization's intention to promote and support employee innovation. Developing new knowledge and insights (Husseina, Mohamad, Noordina, & AmirIshakb, 2006) can put ideas into practice. To get new things or new processes (Schilling, 2008) by new things that arise from the use of knowledge and skills experience and creativity in the development that creates Economic and social benefits (Supakorn Limthammana et al., 2016) by creating innovation From the leadership of the business owner and the cooperation of People at all levels of the organization Organizational environment, knowledge exchange Organizational culture, management, and human resource development, which will bring competitive advantages in the business of community enterprises (Apilak Thamwimutti and Teerawat Chanthuk, 2017) Including characteristics, attitudes, and habits that are preferred for development or embrace innovation Overall enterprise innovation capability It involves bringing new products to market or opening new markets through a combination of strategic focus and innovative

capabilities. Behavioral and process aspects (Anuwat Songsom, 2018). Currently, there are academics and practitioners providing It has many meanings according to knowledge, experience, and understanding of the matter. Different (Mongkol Ekaphan, 2019). The innovation capabilities can be divided as follows:

- **Product innovation (PRD)** The organization encourages Employees express their opinions, innovate, or experiment creatively to meet customer needs. New products and services are presented. that is released into the market faster than competitors Improving and developing products and services (Wang & Ahmed, 2004) and being able to solve problems for consumers. The products created by using innovation can be seen and touched. or in the form of services (Kanokwan Phu Mai, 2016)
- **Process innovation (PRC)** involves improving or creating processes in Operation To increase the efficiency of the work Including management concepts and technology that are used (Wang & Ahmed, 2004) to be modern and meet needs and convenience. New format for customers to raise the efficiency of services and create additional value for the business in a good direction (Edison, Ali, & Torkar, 2013)
- **Behavioral innovation (BVC)** is the creation of a form of innovation culture (Innovative Culture) that creates new ideas and innovations. Expressed at the individual, team and executive level, such innovation is a fundamental factor in the results of innovation creation and the organization can bring out the potential and competency of community enterprises to support business operations in accordance with the current context. Community enterprises can respond to situations in a timely manner. Speed of implementation (Wang & Ahmed, 2004)

C. Organizational performance

Organizational performance is the process of measuring a company's performance (AI-matari, ai- swid; Bt Fadzil, 2014). Modern management includes measuring the rate of sales growth, changes in operations. profit market value growth and customer satisfaction (Santos; Britto,2012) Also, kotze, 2006 stated that the results of operations It is doing the right thing at the right time according to the objectives that have been set in stone.

Organizational performance It is the achievement of goals through the performance of the organization. From a review of related literature, the measurement tools were created as follows: increased market share Sales growth rate increased profits The satisfaction that customers receive has increased. and maintaining a database of old customers and having more new customers.

Measuring organizational performance is important for organizational management. make executives Know the past performance and also be able to predict the future of the business. Measurement of business performance has many dimensions. Some dimensions may be important to one organization but may not be important to another. other organizations The performance of the organization has been defined by scholars such as Wadongo et al, 2010 has given meaning to business performance as showing results or

success from The performance of the business, while De Clercq, Dimov, & Thongpapanl (2010) explained that the performance It is the result of the organization's operations to produce products or services that meet needs and Target customer satisfaction and Sandvik & Sandvik (2003) stated that business performance that is the value that the organization delivers to customers sales growth and market share Types of performance results from the literature review have been presented by academics. There are many dimensions, such as research by Clark (1999) studying innovation strategies that affect marketing performance. Marketing performance can be measured in 2 areas: 1) financial. It is measured by the profits and cash flow of the business. and 2) non-financial aspects Measured by customer satisfaction customer loyalty and brand equity, Lumpkin & Dess (1996) stated that measurement Business operations are divided into 2 types: financial side and business growth data side. As Suphang Nanta (2012) explains, business performance has 2 types: monetary income side. with the image and reputation of the business, and Richard et al. (2009) defined three components of organizational performance: monetary aspects, marketing returns, and returns to shareholders. In addition, Santos & Brito (2012) explained that performance measurement The operations of the business are divided into 2 areas: the economic side and the satisfaction creation side. to the organization's stakeholders

III. HOW TO CONDUCT RESEARCH

A. In this research, the researcher used qualitative research to examine the influence of marketing ability and innovation ability for entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province.

B. The population and sample were 30 entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province.

C. Content scope Study about marketing capabilities and innovation capabilities for entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province. By means of an in-depth interview (In depth Interview)

D. The study period is from 16 June 2023 to 20 September 2023, totaling 3 months.

E. Research tools

Tools used to collect data The researcher used an in-depth interview (In depth Interview), in which the research team created questions to follow the interview guidelines of the informants.

- **Research tools** the researcher used an important tool to collect data by creating a semi-structured questionnaire. By proceeding with the following steps: 1) Study theories, concepts, and principles from books, textbooks, documents, and related research. 2) Study the objectives of the research. 3) Determine the main topics and sub-topics of the interview questions. 4) Consider the questions asked. Use in interviews 5) Improve interview questions. According to the advice of experts
- **Data Collection Method:** The researcher used data collection methods consisting of in-depth interviews. Ready to record audio and moving pictures and taking

notes in the interview The researcher used prepared questions and delved into unclear answers. When the researcher completed the interview The data from the voice recorder will be transcribed into descriptive data. Review the interview, repeating it at least 2 times.

F. Data Analysis

The researcher carried out the data analysis. By using the content analysis technique of Alavinia, Van Duivenhooeden and Burdorf (2007), which is proposed as a technique for analyzing data from reality without diluting the feelings and opinions of the study and looking at the whole picture. of data without separation (Holistic). The above technique is a method of interpretation. (Interpretation approaches) of data obtained from qualitative research interviews.

G. Checking the Reliability of Information

The researcher used data triangulation. (Triangulation) to confirm the reliability of the information as follows: multiple sources of information, including secondary sources and primary data sources from many perspectives, the opinions of the informants include entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

From in-depth interviews, the researcher found key points from 30 entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province. Most confirmed that marketing ability

It is a factor that affects the success of entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province in 3 areas as follows:

In terms of products, it was found that products are always being improved. according to consumer needs There is a survey of customer needs. Always study information about your competitors. and use technology to produce more products than before.

- In terms of price, because entrepreneurs and can control costs Therefore, a price that is appropriate for the situation can be set. This is consistent with the research of Tooksoon and Mohamd 2012, It was found that price marketing ability is the potential to adjust prices to have superior competitiveness and communication marketing ability.
- In terms of distribution channels, it was found that there are both online and offline distribution channels especially online have been used more in the past 3 years since the COVID-19 outbreak. But selling offline, operators give information that they still give the same importance as before because they can reach customers and customers still give more trust.
- In terms of communication, in summary, it was found that entrepreneurs attach great importance to the fact that regular communication with customers builds loyalty with customers and is easy to correct information in cases where customers misunderstand or have questions about the organization or Product. Communication also helps build the image of the organization in various aspects, such as the fact that the organization has a policy to treat

wastewater before leaving the factory. or the organization helping nearby communities.

Innovative ability from interviews with entrepreneurs, it was found that they place great emphasis on process innovation and management innovation, because industrial plants have a large number of personnel, management is quite complex and has many steps from recruitment, selection, employment, welfare. Entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province also added that knowledge management the resources used create work potential and create business success. It comes from the knowledge base that exists within the business. As a result, the business has a higher level of ability due to the application of existing knowledge or the continuous development of new knowledge, this corresponds to the research of (Alchian & Demsetz, 1972). In addition, if the organization has good knowledge management abilities. The organization will be able to use resources more efficiently and create new innovations for the organization (Darroch, 2005). The researcher therefore developed a research hypothesis to test the influence of management on work behavior. creative factors affecting the effectiveness of innovation

The operator provided additional information that Marketing ability Many entrepreneurs are still not very skilled at marketing, and some organizations are not paying enough attention to innovation ability as they should, including a lack of skills and experience in modern marketing.

V. CONCLUSION

Marketing innovation is an important strategy for making difference in the industry inventing, creating, developing, improving new service formats and processes. That responds to needs of customers that are constantly changing on the basis of the need for higher quality services companies that focus on creating and bringing innovation to their services will have an influence on their performance, Innovation in the industry divides innovation in services into four categories, which are:

Management innovation in external communication, innovation in the scope of services and innovation in support work Most service innovations are in the form of new methods of providing services. to customers or consumers, such as using information technology to provide services to customers who come to use the service giving importance of online reviews and sending emails to thank customers for their service. News publicity and present new promotions Increase communication channels with customers.

VI. SUGGESTIONS

This research is a documentary research study and interviews with entrepreneurs in Samut Prakan Province. Marketing ability and innovation ability Therefore, quantitative studies should be conducted and statistical tools should be used to verify this theoretical framework. In order to increase the reliability of the research results.

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